

See discussions, stats, and author profiles for this publication at: <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/306078956>

A comparative study between GSCA-SEM and PLS-SEM

Article · January 2016

DOI: 10.14419/jsp.v1i1.28

CITATIONS

7

READS

440

3 authors:

Asyraf Afthanorhan

Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin | UniSZA

45 PUBLICATIONS 386 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Zainudin Awang

Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin | UniSZA

83 PUBLICATIONS 403 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Mustafa Mamat

Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin

261 PUBLICATIONS 655 CITATIONS

[SEE PROFILE](#)

Some of the authors of this publication are also working on these related projects:

Develop a New Model of Dynamic Postgraduate Supervision Climate in Public Higher Education [View project](#)

Co-operative Enterprise [View project](#)

A comparative study between GSCA-SEM and PLS-SEM

Asyraf Afthanorhan*, Zainudin Awang, Mustafa Mamat

Faculty of Economics and Management Sciences Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin Kampus Gong Badak, 21300 Kuala Terengganu, Terengganu

**Corresponding author E-mail: ash_18raft@yahoo.com*

Abstract

Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) now becomes one of the prominent methods that can ascertain researchers today to analyze the causal effect between latent constructs with multiple variables simultaneously. To add, SEM have two categories namely Covariance and Component or Composite based SEM in which each approaches have their own advantages and disadvantages. Component model have two approaches namely Generalized Structured Component Analysis (GSCA) and Partial Least Square in which both of these applications itself using least square estimator and bootstrap technique in providing of parameter estimate and hypothesis testing. However, there are only a few studies using GSCA-SEM to analyze the relationship between latent construct. Therefore, this study interest to compare the performance of PLS and GSCA in terms of the consistency factor loading, parameter estimation, standard error, and statistical power test using different of sample size. In this study, we perform the medical tourism data as a research subject. The study reveals that the performance GSCA-SEM is better than PLS-SEM in terms of the consistency, standard error and parameter estimate. However, both of this application is really powerful to minimize the type II error.

Keywords: Generalized Structured Component Analysis (GSCA), Partial Least Square, Component Model, Medical Tourism.

AMS Subject Classification:

1. Introduction

Traditionally, two approaches have been employed for Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) namely Covariance Structure Analysis (CSA) and Partial Least Square (PLS) (Anderson and Gerbing, 1988, Joreskog and Wold, 1982). Both of these approaches now have gaining momentum among the researchers and practitioners to analyze the direct effect between explanatory and endogenous constructs. However, Hwang et al., (2010) propose a newly technique as an alternative to CSA called Generalized Structure Component Analysis (GSCA). With respect to model specification, CSA can be known well as common factors whereas PLS and GSCA is equivalent to component or composite modeling.

However, a majority of researchers today from diverse disciplines such as social sciences, management and marketing misunderstand the real theory of SEM. They only learn the application of SEM without attempt to understand the theory underlying these approaches. Hence, the aimed of this research is to do the comparative study between partial least square and generalized structure analysis since both of these approaches are regarded as component modeling. Although the performance for each approach has been discussed previously but mostly of these technique utilize the marketing and management disciplines as their research subject such as (Hwang et al., 2013; Reinartz, Haenlein, Henseler, 2009; Henseler and Dijkstra, 2015; Afthanorhan, 2013; Roldan & Sanchez 2012; Tennehaus, 2011). Therefore, this study using medical tourism as one of the social sciences discipline will be tested for PLS and GSCA approaches. Using medical tourism as a research subject, it can pave away of other readers to really understand the behavior of these approaches that can be handled in other fields as well.

Today, big data issue becomes one of the salient factors across various fields. It was believed that tackling the big data issue can solve a big problem. In order to tackle the big problem for improvement, an appropriate method would be the main source to enable us to identify the pivotal factor that may has potential to give a high impact on the corresponding issues. Appropriate method entails a consistency function of parameters so that the estimation provided is reaching its true probability to reflect the intention of the whole population. Henceforth, this research paper would explain the performance of

PLS and GSCA using medical tourism data. The structure of this paper is as follows: First, we briefly review the background of PLS and GSCA, and discuss the similarities and differences between both of these approaches (PLS and GSCA), values of factor loading, parameter estimates, standard error and statistical power.

2. Background of PLS and GSCA programming

Traditionally, PLS-SEM regarded as the prominent method in which one of the alternative method to CSA-SEM rather than GSCA-SEM. PLS is once initiated by Wold (1982) but has been modified by Lohmoller (1989) to improve the capability of PLS analysis for determining the direct effect between exogenous and endogenous constructs. This particular method was exemplified through LVPLS (Lohmoller, 1984), PLS Graph (Chin, 1992), Smart PLS (Ringle, Wende, and Will, 2005), Visual PLS (Fu, 2006), SPAD PLS (Test & Go, 2006), Warp PLS (2010), PLS GuI SaaS (Hubona, 2014), XLStat-PLS (Addinsoft Sarl, 2007) and Adanco (Henseler, 2014).

Among of these statistical packages, Smart PLS was considered as statistical packages of choice to handle PLS approach. On the other hands, a newly approach namely generalized structured component analysis was implemented by the software program Visual GSCA but now recently rename as GESCA (Hwang, 2009). To explain the characteristics of these approaches, PLS analysis does not work with latent variables but rather with block variables as input data to estimate function of parameter besides to maximize the variance explained for all endogenous construct through sequence of Ordinary Least Square (OLS). Unlike PLS-SEM, GSCA-SEM offers a global least square optimization criterion, which is consistently minimized to obtain the estimates of model parameters. Even GSCA-SEM is not popularly as PLS-SEM but this particular method has gaining attention by the researchers lately since the global criterion enable us to ensure on how fit of our model exhibited.

2.1. Generalized structure component analysis based structural equation modeling (GSCA-SEM)

GSCA-SEM represents a component based approach to structural equation modeling (Tenenhaus, 2008). This approach is defines as follows:

Simple form of SEM formula: $\gamma_i = Wz_j$

Measurement Model formula: $Z_i = C\gamma_i + \varepsilon_i$

Structural Model formula: $\gamma_i = B\gamma_i + \varepsilon_i$

Full Model: $B\gamma_i + \varepsilon_i = W(C\gamma_i + \varepsilon_i)$

Where:

z_i = vector of observed variables for a respondent i ($i = 1, 2, 3, \dots, N$)

γ_i = vector of latent variables for a respondent i

W = matrix consisting of component weight assigned to observed variable

C = Matrix loadings relating of latent variables to observed variables

ε_i = Residual for z_i

B = Matrix of path coefficient between latent variables

ε_j = Residual for γ_j ; the full formula of structural equation model

The formula given is proposed by Hwang et al., (2013) for structural model with GSCA-SEM. Moreover, GSCA-SEM also serve two model specification likely PLS-SEM namely outer model or measurement model and structural or inner model. Outer model would explain the relationship between observed and latent variable. The high relationship between these variable would provide a high factor loading as well as the Fornell criterion. For structural model, this model would explain the relationship between each construct imposed. To add, GSCA-SEM approach using Alternating Least Square algorithm to optimize a global function (de Leeuw, Young, and Takane, 1976). It can alternately updating observed variables weight in one step and inner model weights and observed variables loading in the other steps (Hancock & Mueller, 2013).

Like PLS, GSCA minimize distributional assumption in which can handling the data with small sample size and non-normal data since the implementation of least square algorithm. However, CSA-SEM also can be less restrictive like aforementioned approaches when using unweight least square or asymptotic distribution free estimators (Browne, 1984). During the execution process, the bootstrapping is applied to estimate the standard error and confidence interval in obtaining of probability values for hypothesis testing (Efron, 1982). Unlike PLS-SEM, GSCA-SEM estimate model parameter by consistently minimizing the global optimization criterion (Hwang et al., 2010). In addition, GSCA-SEM have employ a few global scalar function to enable us to identify of how well of our measurement model that involve in this study such as FIT, AFIT, GFI, SRMR, and NPAR for evaluation stage. Therefore, this method is appropriately for confirmatory purpose besides CSA-SEM. In accordance of Hwang et al., (2007), FIT is the proportion of all endogenous construct, so, the range given is from 0 to 1. The larger the value, the more variance in the variable is accounted for the particular model. This threshold value is also suggested for other fitness index.

2.2. Partial least square structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)

Partial Least Square can be known well as variance based structural equation modeling that aimed to maximized the total variance explain for endogenous constructs. This particular method is become preferable option for researchers if the as-

sumption of parametric testing is violated (Ringdon, 2005; Wold, 1975; Afthanorhan, Awang & Asri, 2015). It does not require any distributional assumption to be fulfilled but results in inconsistent parameter estimates if the number of manifest variables for each construct and sample size are consistent at large (Wold, 1975). Therefore, PLS is better suited for situation in which researchers need to predict the relationship between exogenous and endogenous constructs (Theory development or exploratory study). Like GSCA, PLS can deal with unlimited number of formative indicators.

However, PLS do not have any global criterion for evaluation stage to examine the fitness of each model involved in the study. Therefore, many researchers such as (Ronkko and Ylitalo, 2010; Urreta & Marakas, 2012; Ringdon et al., 2012) are argue with the parameter estimates and hypothesis testing of PLS. This is because how PLS can identify the fitness of measurement model if PLS need to quantify the relationship of each construct in a model. If the fitness index is failed, the result exhibited would be affected and thus present the improper solution and factor indeterminacy. PLS-SEM have Q^2 (Stone, 1974; Gaiser, 1977; Afthanorhan, Nazim, & Ahmad, 2015) and f^2 (Cohen, 1988) for evaluating the structural model using blindfolding module. The Stone-Geisser Indicator (Q^2) evaluates how much the model approaches what was expected of it that should be above 0 (Hair et al., 2014; Afthanorhan, Nazim, & Ahmad, 2015). Also, f^2 is evaluated by the ratio between the part explained and non-explained as follows: ($f^2 = R^2 / (1 - R^2)$). Like GSCA, PLS perform the bootstrap to obtain the standard error and confidence interval as well.

3. Methodology

3.1. Values of factor loadings

Consistency is another way to measure the closeness of an estimator θ to the parameter θ in terms of the consistency (Jusoh et al., 2009). In this study, we address the values of the factor loading between these approaches. We interest to identify which approach is better providing a consistent of factor loading with different sample size. In statistical research, the consistent coefficient is one of the significant factor for any simulations studies.

Consequently, we think that this issue will be addressed again using social science data to reveal the truth behind this issue. For us, providing the consistent of factor loading in model specification are necessary to reflect the construct validity of measurement model. In PLS-SEM, fitness index is not provided where it was against with the characters of GSCA-SEM that consists of model fit even the least square estimator embed in this approach. Moreover, GSCA can apply constrained component analysis that may suit as an alternative to confirmatory factor analysis for evaluating the measurement model (Takane, Kiers, & de Leuw, 1995; Afthanorhan, Ahmad & Mamat, 2014; Kiers, Takane, & Ten Berge, 1996).

3.2. Parameter estimation and standard error

Statistical inference consists of those methods to make decision or to draw conclusion about a population, based on information obtained from sample. In statistical inferences, there are two major areas such as parameter estimation and hypothesis testing. Previously, Hwang & Takane (2004) had provided the comparative study between PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM in terms of the parameter estimation and standard error. They found that both of these component models provide quite similar component weight estimates. However, they disclose that the standard error of the estimates from PLS-SEM seem to be bigger than those GSCA-SEM. Thus, this issue causes us to re-do this step using other data sets in order to ensure that this statement can be worth or not in determining these comparative approaches. Plus, both of these components using bootstrap technique on resemble model to stabilize the standard error besides to produce the confidence interval. In this stage, we evaluate the best performance approach based on the smaller error obtained.

3.3. Statistical power of a test

According to Peterman (1990), the power of a statistical test is the probability that will correctly lead to accept or reject of a false null hypothesis. To add, Cohen (1988) stated that the statistical power is the probability that will result in the conclusion that the phenomenon exist. There are two types of statistical power analysis namely retrospective (post hoc) and prospective (a priori). A prospective analysis is used to determine the minimum required of sample size to achieve the goal statistical power test. A retrospective analysis computes the statistical power of a test given sample size and effect size. In this case, we performed a retrospective analysis to determine the performance of statistical power between PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM using medical tourism data. Power of the test is given by:

$$K = 1 - \beta$$

This technique is very important in statistical hypothesis so that the improper solution can be avoided. Improper solution on structural equation modeling refers to cases having one or more parameter with estimation problem (Anderson & Gerbing, 1988). This problem is really associated with the non-convergence parameter estimates. However, non-convergence is basically occurred only when the sample size is too small and the factor loading that reflect the character of latent constructs is too poor (Ding, Velicer, & Harlow, 1995). Thus, this statistical power will be conducted on PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM in obtaining of how well these approaches able minimizes the probability of type II error in which equivalent to maximize the quantity of $1 - \beta$. We will perform this technique as the last stage inferential statistics.

3.4. Procedure statistical inferential

During the inferential stage, we perform the comparison study between PLS and GSCA in terms of the values of factor loading, parameter estimates, statistical power test and standard error with different of sample size. Chin and Newsted (1999) contend that PLS can provide meaningful information from sample size as low as 20. With this consistent thinking, we start the simulation study from 50 of sample size followed by 200, 500 and 1,000. With its simulation study, we could compare the performance of PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM. As mentioned earlier, we use the medical tourism model where has being confirmed by Awang et al., (2015).

Table 1: Comparison of Factor Loadings

Construct	PLS-SEM				GSCA-SEM			
	50	200	500	1000	50	200	500	1000
Physical Infrastructure	50	200	500	1000	50	200	500	1000
P1	0.642	0.684	0.684	0.681	0.629	0.670	0.672	0.668
P2	0.710	0.677	0.684	0.685	0.709	0.671	0.679	0.678
P3	0.732	0.771	0.753	0.752	0.732	0.779	0.756	0.757
P4	0.837	0.787	0.779	0.774	0.839	0.789	0.782	0.777
P5	0.884	0.801	0.801	0.804	0.837	0.800	0.800	0.804
P6	0.803	0.836	0.832	0.827	0.806	0.839	0.836	0.832
P7	0.792	0.844	0.834	0.830	0.798	0.850	0.839	0.836
P8	0.778	0.819	0.806	0.797	0.773	0.821	0.809	0.800
Service Quality	50	200	500	1000	50	200	500	1000
SQ1	0.900	0.819	0.798	0.792	0.888	0.815	0.797	0.790
SQ2	0.840	0.808	0.817	0.816	0.833	0.816	0.821	0.819
SQ3	0.774	0.839	0.848	0.851	0.773	0.837	0.845	0.848
SQ4	0.889	0.844	0.850	0.852	0.889	0.851	0.855	0.856
SQ5	0.778	0.822	0.802	0.792	0.810	0.835	0.811	0.799
SQ6	0.819	0.817	0.787	0.762	0.822	0.813	0.787	0.764
SQ7	0.542	0.697	0.698	0.703	0.573	0.696	0.699	0.705
SQ8	0.690	0.626	0.661	0.672	0.665	0.605	0.646	0.659
Patient Satisfaction	50	200	500	1000	50	200	500	1000
PS1	0.754	0.797	0.782	0.779	0.777	0.815	0.799	0.795
PS2	0.762	0.770	0.775	0.779	0.779	0.786	0.790	0.793
PS3	0.835	0.779	0.780	0.785	0.832	0.777	0.781	0.788
PS4	0.889	0.802	0.797	0.792	0.884	0.814	0.809	0.804
PS5	0.823	0.769	0.758	0.758	0.806	0.767	0.760	0.760
PS6	0.640	0.710	0.728	0.734	0.637	0.692	0.707	0.714
PS7	0.545	0.694	0.724	0.731	0.539	0.673	0.702	0.710
Patient Loyalty	50	200	500	1000	50	200	500	1000
PL1	0.595	0.686	0.717	0.792	0.588	0.675	0.711	0.726
PL2	0.758	0.661	0.696	0.710	0.749	0.655	0.694	0.708
PL3	0.618	0.493	0.497	0.510	0.829	0.828	0.821	0.818
PL4	0.828	0.832	0.824	0.821	0.767	0.820	0.824	0.824
PL5	0.768	0.816	0.819	0.819	0.636	0.502	0.505	0.518

Table 1 present the finding of factor loading for each correspondent latent constructs with different implementation of SEM. As aforementioned, we aimed to identify to what extent the factor loadings consistent or different sample size. We split the data sets into four samples properties that consist of 50, 200, 500, and 1,000 of sample size with identical measurement model. Then after, this measurement model will be executed with PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM to obtain factor loadings of each constructs. Both of this method can handle the data sets with small sample size since practiced of least square estimator.

We found that that GSCA-SEM is better than PLS-SEM to handle small data sets as enumerated in Figure 1 which is at the threshold of 50 of sample size at the initial stage. However, both of these approaches suggest the consistency of factor loading at the 200 of sample size. Means that, PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM approaches are perceives consistent of factor loading at 200 of samples. This result is meeting with the theory of Boyle et al., (1995) to suggest that structural equation modeling should have at least 200 of sample size for a good starting point. For PLS-SEM, Wold (1985) which is the father of PLS noted that PLS estimators for path coefficient and loadings do not tend the probability to the true values when the sample size increases, so they are not consistency in the nature sense. However, he pointed out the path estimate and factor loadings tend to the true value when the number of reflective indicators and latent constructs are increases as well. Therefore, this statement can be our evidence to support of our finding that GSCA-SEM is more relevance to handle the small data sets rather than PLS-SEM. To address both of these approaches, probability of block of indicator variables to reach the consistency of factor loadings in GSCA-SEM is higher than PLS-SEM.

This situation can be seen at the Table 1 and Figure 1 to become our evidence that the performance of GSCA-SEM in obtaining of loadings is continuously consistence occurs at every construct involved. We then estimated the model parameter both with PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM. At the next step, we compare the parameter estimate and standard error by adapting this approach so that we could assess its performance. Finally, inference statistics comprised of the occurrence of Type I and Type II error using the statistical power test. This technique is important to let us discover the powerful of the statistical

test for each approach applied. As a proof, Goodhue et al. (2006, 2012), or Reinartz et al. (2009) have often focused on the statistical power when comes to the comparing of the performance approaches.

Fig. 1: Factor Loading

Table 2: Comparison of Parameter Estimation

Construct	Sample Size	PLS	GSCA
		Parameter Estimate	Parameter Estimate
Physical Infrastructure → Patient Loyalty	50	0.6649***	0.643***
	200	0.6872***	0.626***
	500	0.6545***	0.607***
	1000	0.6293***	0.589***
Physical Infrastructure → Patient Satisfaction	50	0.3311***	0.348**
	200	0.4708***	0.469***
	500	0.4528***	0.449***
	1000	0.4542***	0.449***
Service Quality → Patient Loyalty	50	0.2203***	0.173
	200	0.2028***	0.192***
	500	0.2417***	0.228***
	1000	0.2683***	0.255***
Service Quality → Patient Satisfaction	50	0.2595**	0.237
	200	0.0697	0.063
	500	0.1056	0.103**
	1000	0.1062	0.105***
Patient Satisfaction → Patient Loyalty	50	0.1370*	0.116
	200	0.1387**	0.137***
	500	0.1147	0.113***
	1000	0.0978	0.098***

Note:

*: Significant at 0.10 (90% confidence level)

**: Significant at 0.05 (95% confidence level)

***: Significant at 0.01 (99% confidence level)

Thus far, there are little attention has been paid to the possibility that PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM, if used to estimate the common factor model in which one to overestimate path coefficient. Dijkstra & Henseler (2015) contend that inflated path coefficient increase the danger of Type 1 errors (false positive), which means that an effect may be considered significant even though it does not actually present in the real situation. To add, they also pointed out that the estimate is safer if PLS-SEM underestimate the true parameter (Type II error) rather than overestimate the true parameter (Type 1 error). Even Monte Carlo simulation has been suggested by previous research to quantify the performance of PLS and GSCA, but this particular method is do not investigate the false positive (Lu et al. 2011; Reinartz et al. 2009). In social sciences, false positive are often regarded as a more severe problem than false negative (Cohen, 1988). So, this is the reason why we compare the path coefficient of PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM in order to illuminate the ambiguities of other researchers and readers to use SEM properly. For us, misleading estimate can lead to erroneous hypothesis testing and subsequent impair the conclusion and recommendation that will be used for managerial decision.

Table 2 shows that the result of parameter estimates for every constructs that provided in corresponding method program. PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM are approve that physical infrastructure and service quality are significant and direct effect on patient loyalty meanwhile physical infrastructure are also significant on patient satisfaction. In this situation, the problem is arise when service quality on patient satisfaction and patient satisfaction on patient loyalty is suggest the diverse decision between these techniques. Then, as a researcher, how we want to make a decision if the result obtained is totally different. So, this is the reason why this study is important to compare between these approaches and should be stressed among the scholars today. Plus, the theory likely patient satisfaction on patient loyalty is surely significant based on the previous study (Atkins, Marshall, & Javalgi, 1995; Wu, 2011; Kessler & Lod, 2011; Fisk et al., 1990) as well as service quality on patient satisfaction (Wu, 2011; Taylor and Cronin, 1993; Andaleeb 2001).

Surprisingly, PLS-SEM which one of the prominent approaches shows contravenes finding compare with previous theories. In fact, these important theories are acceptable for any researchers especially from management and marketing disciplines. Nevertheless, GSCA-SEM shows equivalent finding with the previous theory. Consequently, we posit that GSCA-SEM is better than PLS-SEM in terms of not improper solution in obtaining true value for hypothesis testing. Without fully understand the theory relies behind this algorithm, the result would be affected and it actually our role to determine which technique is appropriate for our research. As usual, Hair et al (2014) and Sarstedt et. al., (2012) promising that PLS-SEM often serve as a basis of theory development but this statement is contradict with Chin (2010) thinking to claim that PLS can be construed appropriate in a confirmatory sense. In order to identify which technique is relevant for managerial decision, we compare the standard error and statistical power at the next discussion.

Table 3: Comparison of Standard Error

Construct	Sample Size	PLS Standard Error	GSCA Standard Error
Physical Infrastructure → Patient Loyalty	50	0.0630	0.102
	200	0.0705	0.059
	500	0.0755	0.053
	1000	0.0791	0.025
Physical Infrastructure → Patient Satisfaction	50	0.0995	0.174
	200	0.1187	0.086
	500	0.1145	0.040
	1000	0.1132	0.037
Service Quality → Patient Loyalty	50	0.0616	0.108
	200	0.0708	0.057
	500	0.0772	0.034
	1000	0.0783	0.025
Service Quality → Patient Satisfaction	50	0.1051	0.213
	200	0.1306	0.088
	500	0.1170	0.053
	1000	0.1273	0.038
Patient Satisfaction → Patient Loyalty	50	0.0729	0.109
	200	0.0693	0.047
	500	0.0716	0.030
	1000	0.0721	0.022

Standard error statistics are class of inferential statistics that permit the researcher to construct the confidence intervals about the obtained sample statistics in which drawn from population (McHugh, 2007; Awang, Afthanorhan, & Asri, 2015). They contemplated that the smaller the standard error, the closer the sample of statistics is to the population parameter. Standard error is appearing to be similar with standard deviation but they are used differently. The standard deviation is a measure of the variability of sample in a while standard error is a measure of the variability of the sampling distribution. With this consistent thinking, we opined that the comparison between of standard error between these approaches should be considered as an alternative to claim the efficiency of parameter estimate. Table 3 present the result of standard error between PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM. At sample size of 50, PLS-SEM produce less standard error compare to GSCA-SEM but the result become reversed once the sample size become increases. In this case, GSCA-SEM produces less standard error when the sample size increases. This finding is surely meet with the previous original research by Hwang & Takane (2004). So, this is the reason of why the hypothesis testing between these approaches becomes different. In terms of the standard error, GSCA-SEM is more relevant to be considered since the smaller value of error obtained prevailing of large sample size. In addition, it seems that the result from GSCA-SEM is more reliable since the smaller value of error and the consistency of factor loading thus far. However, our finding is inadequate if we do not test the statistical power for these techniques. As aforementioned, this technique is the last inferential stage to find the power of the test, we hold the probability of a type II error fixed and look for the test statistic that minimize the probability of type II error is equivalent to minimizing power. When testing $H_0: \theta = \theta$ against $H_1: \theta \neq \theta$, quantity $1-\beta$ is referred as the power of the test at $\theta = \theta$.

Table 4: Statistical Power Test

Construct	Sample Size	PLS-SEM		GSCA-SEM	
		Observed R ²	Power of test	Observed R ²	Power of test
Patient Satisfaction	50	27.0%	95.2%	28.9%	95.1%
	200	26.3%	95.2%	27.9%	95.2%
	500	27.0%	95.2%	28.5%	95.1%
	1000	27.4%	95.2%	28.9%	95.0%
Patient Loyalty	50	67.1%	95.6%	67.2%	95.7%
	200	69.1%	95.5%	69.2%	95.5%
	500	68.2%	95.2%	68.3%	95.3%
	1000	67.8%	95.1%	67.9%	95.2%

Table 4 provides an overview of the statistical power and observed coefficient of determination of each technique. R² can be obtained for endogenous constructs as the total variation that is has been explained from the presence of exogenous constructs. Our analysis began with the situation of removal any item that may potential to harm the model such as multicollinearity problem. The model in GSCA-SEM is achieving the requirement of fitness by referring the model fit provided in GESCA programming. For PLS-SEM, the fitness of measurement model like GoF can be implemented but Henseler and Sarstedt (2012) remarked that the behavior of this particular fitness is not suitable for model validation. Therefore, the model validation can be presented for structural model such as f² (effect size) and Q² (predictive relevance). The statistical power test is calculated as proposed by Cohen (1992). In his article, he recommends a level statistical power of 0.80 or 80%.Based on this, we use another free statistical programming namely G* Power 3.1.9 to carry out power analyses specif-

ic to model setup. In this case, we found that GSCA-SEM was capable of detecting a small effect regardless of the sample size performed proportionate with PLS-SEM.

However, Both of these approach reached 80 percent in the case of 50, 200, 500 and 1,000 observations. These finding is make sense to meet the requirement of power of test since (Henseler & Dijkstra, 2015; Hwang & Takane, 2004) they concur to believe that both of these component models are powerful to minimize type II error (rejecting false hypothesis). In addition, the observed coefficient of determination for each approach is almost similar to produce a high total variation of explaining the whole structural model. In addition, Hair et al., (2014) contends that the best effect of R^2 is 0.36 or 36% above followed by 0.13 or 13% as median effect and 0.20 or 2% as a lowest effect. A mean that, both approaches is meet with its character to aim at to maximize the variance of endogenous construct.

4. Conclusion and recommendation

As explained earlier, the aimed of this paper to compare the performance of PLS-SEM and GSCA-SEM approaches which are composed in the same category as component or composite modeling. We use the medical tourism data as a research subject to achieve our goal for explaining the behavior or character these particular approaches. In comparative purpose, we differentiate both of these component models in terms of consistency of factor loadings, parameter estimate, standard error and statistical power test. Thus far, we found that GSCA-SEM is better than PLS-SEM in terms of the consistency of factor loadings/outer loadings, parameter estimate and standard error. However, both of these approaches are meet the requirement of function of power test. So, there are fourfold will be summarized based on our finding presented. We began the explanation of the values of factor loading.

Factor loading can be known as outer model that used to reflect the behavior of the main latent construct. Therefore, consistent factor loading is important in model specification for explaining the structure model. During the model validation, GSCA-SEM serve global scalar function to enable us identify of which items are suitable for subsequent analysis rather than PLS-SEM. Due to the poor of model fit of PLS-SEM, the factor loadings are inconsistent and furthers effect on parameter estimation. Table 1 is one of our evidence to support of our ideas.

Secondly, parameter estimation is one of the major areas in statistical hypothesis. As enumerated in Table 2, both of these component shows different decision especially at the service quality on patient satisfaction and patient satisfaction on patient loyalty. Reality, most of the previous research endorse these factors should be significant; however, GSCA-SEM is the only one approach meet this theory. Although Reinartz, Haenlien, & Henseler (2009), Hair et al., (2014), and Ringle, Silva, & Bido, (2014) believe that PLS-SEM provides proper solution in statistical inference based on their previous discussion, yet, the outcome of the current study for PLS-SEM has less efficient compare to GSCA-SEM.

Thirdly, we create Table 3 that only provided of standard error in order to illuminate the explanation step by step. Based on this finding, we support the theory of Hwang & Takane (2004) to inform that the standard error in PLS-SEM is bigger than GSCA-SEM. Strictly speaking, the large standard error tend to undermine the direct effect of estimation. High standard error is parallel with the high multicollinearity problem.

Finally, we perform statistical power as presented in Table 4. In this case, both of these components are meet the requirement of power analysis since higher than 80%. Plus, R^2 obtained seem quite high (Above 26%) to evaluate the portion variances of the endogenous variables, which is explained by structural model

For future research, we may emphasize the performance of this component model with multi-group analysis. This is because GSCA-SEM provides constraint in its application that is not provided in PLS-SEM. We interest to identify to what extend the performance of PLS-SEM when comparing with GSCA-SEM if the direct effect was influence by the inclusion of an external factors.

References

- [1] Addinsoft SARL (2007–2008) XLSTAT-PLSPM. Paris, France. <http://www.xlstat.com/en/products/xlstatplspm/>
- [2] Afthanorhan, B. W. (2013). A Comparison Of Partial Least Square Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) and Covariance Based Structural Equation Modeling (CB-SEM) for Confirmatory Factor Analysis.
- [3] Afthanorhan, W. M. A. B. W., Ahmad, S., & Mamat, I. (2014). Pooled Confirmatory Factor Analysis (PCFA) Using Structural Equation Modeling on Volunteerism Program: A Step by Step Approach. *International Journal of Asian Social Science*, 4(5), 642-653.
- [4] Afthanorhan, A., Nazim, A., & Ahmad, S. A parametric approach to partial least square structural equation modeling of multigroup analysis (PLS-MGA).
- [5] Afthanorhan, A., Nazim, A., & Ahmad, S. (2014). A parametric approach to partial least square structural equation modeling of multigroup analysis (PLS-MGA). *International Journal of Economic, Commerce, and Management*, 2(10), 15.
- [6] Awang, Z., Afthanorhan, A., & Asri, M. A. M. (2015). Parametric and Non Parametric Approach in Structural Equation Modeling (SEM): The Application of Bootstrapping. *Modern Applied Science*, 9(9), 58. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5539/mas.v9n9p58>.
- [7] Awang, Z., Afthanorhan, A., Mohamad, M., & Asri, M. A. M. (2015). An evaluation of measurement model for medical tourism research: the confirmatory factor analysis approach. *International Journal of Tourism Policy*, 6(1), 29-45. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1504/IJTP.2015.075141>.
- [8] Aguirre-Urreta, M. I., & Marakas, G. M. (2012). Revisiting Bias Due to Construct Misspecification: Different Results from Considering Coefficients in Standardized Form. *MIS Quarterly*, 36(1), 123-138.
- [9] Andaleeb, S. S. (2001). Service quality perceptions and patient satisfaction: a study of hospitals in a developing country. *Social science & medicine*, 52(9), 1359-1370. [http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536\(00\)00235-5](http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/S0277-9536(00)00235-5).

- [10] Anderson, J. C., & Gerbing, D. W. (1988). Structural equation modeling in practice: A review and recommended two-step approach. *Psychological bulletin*, 103(3), 411. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1037/0033-2909.103.3.411>.
- [11] Atkins, P. M., Marshall, B. S., & Javalgi, R. G. (1995). Happy employees lead to loyal patients. Survey of nurses and patients shows a strong link between employee satisfaction and patient loyalty. *Journal of health care marketing*, 16(4), 14-23.
- [12] Boyle, G. J., Borg, M. G., Falzon, J. M., & Baglioni, A. J. (1995). A structural model of the dimensions of teacher stress. *British Journal of Educational Psychology*, 65(1), 49-67. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8279.1995.tb01130.x>.
- [13] Chin, W. W. (1993-2003). PLS Graph – Version 3.0. Soft Modeling Inc
- [14] Chin, W. W. (2001). PLS-Graph user's guide. CT Bauer College of Business, University of Houston, USA.
- [15] Chin, W. W., & Newsted, P. R. (1999). Structural equation modeling analysis with small samples using partial least squares.
- [16] Cohen, J. (1988). *Statistical power analysis for the behavioral sciences* (2nd ed.). Hillsdale, NJ: Erlbaum.
- [17] Cohen, J. (1992). Statistical power analysis. Current directions in psychological science, 98-101. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/1467-8721.ep10768783>.
- [18] Cudeck, R., & Browne, M. W. (1983). Cross-validation of covariance structures. *Multivariate Behavioral Research*, 18(2), 147-167. http://dx.doi.org/10.1207/s15327906mbr1802_2.
- [19] De Leeuw, J., Young, F. W., & Takane, Y. (1976). Additive structure in qualitative data: An alternating least squares method with optimal scaling features. *Psychometrika*, 41(4), 471-503. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02296971>.
- [20] Dijkstra, T. K., & Henseler, J. (2015). Consistent and asymptotically normal PLS estimators for linear structural equations. *Computational statistics & data analysis*, 81, 10-23. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.csda.2014.07.008>.
- [21] Dijkstra, T. K., & Henseler, J. (2015). Consistent partial least squares path modeling. *MIS Quarterly*.
- [22] Ding, L., Velicer, W. F., & Harlow, L. L. (1995). Effects of estimation methods, number of indicators per factor, and improper solutions on structural equation modeling fit indices. *Structural Equation Modeling: A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 2(2), 119-143. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/10705519509540000>.
- [23] Efron, B., & Efron, B. (1982). *The jackknife, the bootstrap and other resampling plans* (Vol. 38). Philadelphia: Society for industrial and applied mathematics. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1137/1.9781611970319>.
- [24] Fisk, T. A., Brown, C. J., Cannizzaro, K. G., & Naftal, B. (1990). Creating patient satisfaction and loyalty. *Journal of health care marketing*, 10(2), 5-15.
- [25] Fu, J.-R. (2006b). VisualPLS – Partial Least Square (PLS) Regression – An Enhanced GUI for Lvpls (PLS 1.8 PC) Version 1.04. <http://www2.kuas.edu.tw/prof/fred/vpls/index.html>.
- [26] Gaisser, T. K., & Hillas, A. M. (1977). Reliability of the method of constant intensity cuts for reconstructing the average development of vertical showers. In *International Cosmic Ray Conference* (Vol. 8, pp. 353-357).
- [27] Geoffrey Hubona (2014), PLS Gui SaaS (accessed November 2014), [available at <http://pls-gui.com/>].
- [28] Goodhue, D. L., Lewis, W., & Thompson, R. (2012). Does PLS have advantages for small sample size or non-normal data?. *Mis Quarterly*, 36(3), 891-1001.
- [29] Goodhue, D., Lewis, W., & Thompson, R. (2006, January). PLS, small sample size, and statistical power in MIS research. In *System Sciences, 2006. HICSS'06. Proceedings of the 39th Annual Hawaii International Conference on* (Vol. 8, pp. 202b-202b). IEEE. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1109/hicss.2006.381>.
- [30] Hair Jr, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., & Sarstedt, M. (2014). *A primer on partial least squares structural equation modeling (PLS-SEM)*. Sage Publications.
- [31] Hair, J. F., Ringle, C. M., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Editorial-partial least squares structural equation modeling: Rigorous applications, better results and higher acceptance. *Long Range Planning*, 46(1-2), 1-12. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2013.01.001>.
- [32] Hancock, G. R., & Mueller, R. O. (Eds.). (2013). *Structural equation modeling: A second course*. Iap.
- [33] Henseler and Dijkstra (2014), ADANCO 1.0 (accessed December 2014), [available at <http://www.composite-modeling.com/get-adanco/>].
- [34] Henseler, J., & Sarstedt, M. (2013). Goodness-of-fit indices for partial least squares path modeling. *Computational Statistics*, 28(2), 565-580. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s00180-012-0317-1>.
- [35] Hwang, H., & Takane, Y. (2004). Generalized structured component analysis. *Psychometrika*, 69(1), 81-99. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02295841>.
- [36] Hwang, H., Jung, K., Takane, Y., & Woodward, T. S. (2013). A unified approach to multiple-set canonical correlation analysis and principal components analysis. *British Journal of Mathematical and Statistical Psychology*, 66(2), 308-321. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1111/j.2044-8317.2012.02052.x>.
- [37] Hwang, H., Malhotra, N. K., Kim, Y., Tomiuk, M. A., & Hong, S. (2010). A comparative study on parameter recovery of three approaches to structural equation modeling. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 47(4), 699-712. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1509/jmkr.47.4.699>.
- [38] Hwang, Heungsun and Naresh K. Malhotra (2007), "Multilevel Generalized Structured Component Analysis," *Behaviormetrika*, 34 (2), 95-109 <http://dx.doi.org/10.2333/bhmk.34.95>.
- [39] Hwang, Heungsun (2009a), GeSCA, (accessed April 12, 2010), [available at <http://www.sem-gesca.org/>].
- [40] Jöreskog, K. G., & Wold, H. O. (1982). *Systems under indirect observation: Causality, structure, prediction* (Vol. 139). North Holland.
- [41] Jusoh Yaacob, Nasuhar Aziz, Zuraida Jaafar, Syaliza Yusof, Safwati Ibrahim (2009). *Probability & Statistics*. Unpublished manual.
- [42] Kessler, D. P., & Mylod, D. (2011). Does patient satisfaction affect patient loyalty?. *International journal of health care quality assurance*, 24(4), 266-273. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/09526861111125570>.
- [43] Kiers, H. A., Takane, Y., & ten Berge, J. M. (1996). The analysis of multitrait-multimethod matrices via constrained components analysis. *Psychometrika*, 61(4), 601-628. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02294039>.
- [44] Lohmoller, J.B. (1984). *LVPLS, program manual. Latent variable path analysis with partial least-squares estimation*, Koln, Germany: Zentralarchiv for empirische Sozsaforchung.
- [45] Lohmoller, J.B. (1989). *Latent variable path modeling with partial least square*. Heidelberg, Germany; Physica-Verlag. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/978-3-642-52512-4>.
- [46] Lu, I. R., Kwan, E., Thomas, D. R., & Cedzynski, M. (2011). Two new methods for estimating structural equation models: An illustration and a comparison with two established methods. *International Journal of Research in Marketing*, 28(3), 258-268. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2011.03.006>.

- [47] Mary L. McHugh. Standard error: meaning and interpretation. *Biochemia Medica* 2008;18(1):7-13. <http://dx.doi.org/10.11613/BM.2008.002>.
- [48] Ned Kock (2010), Warp PLS (accessed 2010), [available at <http://www.scriptwarp.com/warppls/>].
- [49] Peterman, R. M. (1990). Statistical power analysis can improve fisheries research and management. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences*, 47(1), 2-15. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1139/f90-001>.
- [50] Reinartz, W., Haenlein, M., & Henseler, J. (2009). An empirical comparison of the efficacy of covariance-based and variance-based SEM. *International Journal of research in Marketing*, 26(4), 332-344. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2009.08.001>.
- [51] Reinartz, W., Haenlein, M., & Henseler, J. (2009). An empirical comparison of the efficacy of covariance-based and variance-based SEM. *International Journal of research in Marketing*, 26(4), 332-344. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.ijresmar.2009.08.001>.
- [52] Rigdon, E. E. (2005). Structural equation modeling: nontraditional alternatives. *Encyclopedia of statistics in behavioral science*. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1002/0470013192.bsa602>.
- [53] Rigdon, E. E. (2012). Rethinking partial least squares path modeling: in praise of simple methods. *Long Range Planning*, 45(5), 341-358. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2012.09.010>.
- [54] Ringle CM, Wende S, Will A (2005) SmartPLS 2.0 M3. University of Hamburg, Hamburg, Germany. <http://www.smartpls.de>
- [55] Roldán, J. L., & Sánchez-Franco, M. J. (2012). Variance-Based Structural Equation Modeling: Guidelines for Using Partial Least Squares. *Research methodologies, innovations and philosophies in software systems engineering and information systems*, 193. <http://dx.doi.org/10.4018/978-1-4666-0179-6.ch010>.
- [56] Rönkkö, M., & Ylitalo, J. (2010, December). Construct Validity in Partial Least Squares Path Modeling. In ICIS (p. 155).
- [57] Sarstedt, M., Ringle, C. M., Henseler, J., & Hair, J. F. (2014). On the emancipation of PLS-SEM: A commentary on Rigdon (2012). *Long range planning*, 47(3), 154-160. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.lrp.2014.02.007>.
- [58] Stone, M. (1974). Cross-validated choice and assessment of statistical predictions. *Journal of the Royal Statistical Society. Series B (Methodological)*, 111-147.
- [59] Takane, Y., Kiers, H. A., & de Leeuw, J. (1995). Component analysis with different sets of constraints on different dimensions. *Psychometrika*, 60(2), 259-280. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/BF02301416>.
- [60] Taylor, S. A., & Cronin Jr, J. J. (1993). Modeling patient satisfaction and service quality. *Journal of health care marketing*, 14(1), 34-44.
- [61] Tenenhaus A, Tenenhaus M (2011) Regularized generalized canonical correlation analysis. *Psychometrika* 76(2):257–284 <http://dx.doi.org/10.1007/s11336-011-9206-8>.
- [62] Tenenhaus, M. (2008). Component-based structural equation modelling. *Total quality management*, 19(7-8), 871-886. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1080/14783360802159543>.
- [63] Test&Go (2006). Spad Version 6.0.0. Paris, France.
- [64] Wold, H. (1975). Soft modeling by latent variables: the nonlinear iterative partial least squares approach. *Perspectives in probability and statistics, papers in honour of MS Bartlett*, 520-540.
- [65] Wold, H. (1985). Partial least squares. *Encyclopedia of statistical sciences*.
- [66] Wu, C. C. (2011). The impact of hospital brand image on service quality, patient satisfaction and loyalty. *African Journal of Business Management*, 5(12), 4873-4882.